

A STUDY OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS AND MOTIVATION OF PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS IN RELATION TO THEIR ACHIEVEMENT AND ATTITUDE TO WARDS TEACHING

Deo Nandan Singh

Ph.D. Research Scholar

IASE, Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi-110025

ABSTRACT:

The purpose of the present study is to investigate interrelationships amongst four variables i.e. Socio-Economic Status, Motivation, Achievement and Attitude of Pre-Service Teachers. The Researcher took 333 prospective teachers as sample from four randomly selected B.Ed. colleges affiliated to Guru Govind Singh Indraprastha University, New Delhi. The Investigator used Socio-Economic Status Scale developed by Prof. R.P.Verma, Saxena & Mishra, Motivation Analysis Test by Cattell and Horn, Teacher Attitude Inventory by Dr.S.P.Ahluwalia and the Achievement Test developed by the Investigator himself. Data interpretation and analysis was done through various statistical techniques like Mean, SD, Percentage, t-Value, Bi-Variate & Multi Variate Correlation and Regression Analysis. The major findings of the study were: 1) Majority of Pre-Service Teachers studying in the University, were of High SES. 2) Around one fourth of Pre-Service Teachers were of Very High SES. 3) Majority of them had average level of motivation. 4) SES was significantly correlated to the Achievement and Attitude of Pre-Service Teachers. 5) Very High SES Pre-Service Teachers had highest level of Motivation and Achievement. 6) No significant correlation was found between Motivation and Attitude. 7) Majority of Pre-Service Teachers had Average Achievement. 8) Regarding joint contribution, SES is more significant factor than Motivation in the prediction of Achievement as well as Teaching Attitude of Pre-Service Teachers.

Key Words: Socio-Economic Status (SES), Motivation, Pre-Service Teachers, Achievement

INTRODUCTION

For transforming a society education is the most effective instrument and the teachers are the most important agent of this transformation process. It is the education which brings knowledge, emotional integration, efficiency, prosperity, harmony and rational thinking to the society through different sources but the teacher is the most important and influencing agent of such transformations. Even in this technologically very advanced era the teachers are the real builders of the future generation in every society. The role of present teachers has become more challenging, complex and significant because today's generation is much sensitive & different from past. In such a situation it is extremely important for every society, community and nations to know about the individuals who are performing the task of shaping the future of present generation because the psycho-social characteristics of teachers have more or less impact on the learners. The quality of education in a society is a direct consequence and outcome of the quality of teachers, so the study of psycho-social traits held by them is very important and interesting. How a teacher performs his duty as a teacher is dependent to a great extent on their psycho-social traits like socio-economic status, family environment, motivation, attitude, interest, intelligence, learning abilities and finally their achievement as a professional. It is very important and interesting to know the interrelationships among various psycho-social factors contributing in making of a teacher. The physical and socio-economic environment of different communities shows very wide contrasts on teachers. The training of an individual is not limited to the places of formal education but also related to their psycho-social traits. Socio-Economic Status' dimensions contribute in their psycho-social aspects of personality. All the individuals have different levels of motivation which direct their actions and behavior towards any

goal. SES and motivation of pre-service teachers also contribute in their achievement and attitude towards the profession.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS OF THE TERMS USED

Socio-Economic Status: Socio-Economic Status of an individual is his place of honor and power (economic, political, academic etc.) among the people of his society. It connotes his competence to command respect of the people around him and also his capacity to originate others that is to make others do what he likes them to do. It is a continuum which has its lower and upper ends. It also denotes his standard of living and thinking. (Manual of Socio-Economic Status Scale developed by Prof. R.P.Verma, Saxena & Mishra)

Motivation: Motivation is the arousal and influence of different ergs and sentiments on the individuals' behavior towards specific goals. (Manual of MAT by Cattell and Horn)

Pre-Service teachers: Pre-service teachers are those who enrolled for B.Ed. degree program and will enter into a long term relationship with schools so that they may contribute to the curriculum, students' learning and general life of the school.

Achievement: Overall performance of Pre-Service Teachers on a Self Constructed Test measuring specific objectives like knowledge, understanding, skill and application towards the concepts related to Core papers and Practical papers taught in B.Ed. course [2013-2014] of Guru Govind Singh Indraprastha University, Delhi.

Attitude: Attitude towards teaching is considered as the overall feelings of the pre-service teachers towards teaching profession, classroom teaching, child centered practices, educational process, students and teachers. In addition a teacher's attitudes not only affect his behavior in the classroom but also influence the behavior of his students. (Manual of TAI developed by Dr. S.P.Ahluwalia)

DELIMITATIONS

1. The study is confined to four colleges affiliated to GGSIPU, New Delhi
2. Only B.Ed. students have been taken as Pre-Service Teachers
3. No Gender difference has been taken into consideration
4. Only Core Papers and Practical papers of B.Ed. curriculum (session: 2013-14) of G.G.S.I.P.University taken for developing Achievement Test.
5. Only Total Motivation has been taken into consideration not dimensionwise.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the Socio-Economic Status of Pre-Service Teachers
2. To study the Motivation of Pre-Service Teachers
3. To study the Achievement of Pre-Service Teachers
4. To study the Relationship between:
 - A. Socio-Economic Status and Achievement of Pre-Service Teachers
 - B. Motivation and Achievement of Pre-Service Teachers
5. To study the specific and joint contribution of SES and motivation on Achievement and attitude of Pre-Service Teachers

METHODOLOGY

Sample for the Study: The researcher used survey method to collect data randomly selected four B.Ed. colleges affiliated to Guru Govind Singh Indraprastha University; New Delhi for a sample of 333 B.Ed. students.

Tools Employed: Socio-Economic Status Scale developed by Prof. R.P.Verma, Saxena & Mishra (2009), Motivation Analysis Test by Cattell and Horn (Revised Edition), Teacher Attitude Inventory by Dr.S.P.Ahluwalia and the Achievement Test developed by the Investigator himself.

Statistical Techniques used: For analysis and interpretation of data the researcher used Mean, Median,

Mode, Standard Deviation, Percentage, t-Value, Bi-Variate, Multi Viriate Co-relation Technique & step-wise Multiple Regression Analysis. Bi-Variate correlation was established between SES & Motivation, SES & Achievement, Motivation & Achievement and measured the strength of their relationship. Step-wise Multiple Regressions was used to check the Joint Contribution of Socio-Economic Status & Motivation on the dependent variable Achievement and Attitude of Pre-Service Teachers towards teaching.

RESULT ANALYSIS & FINDINGS

A. Socio-Economic Status of Pre-Service Teachers:

For this purpose Mean, Standard Deviation and Percentage were calculated in Table no. 1 and has been depicted through Bar Diagrams in figure no. 1 and 2 respectively.

Table No. 1 (Showing Mean Value and Standard Deviation of SES in different institutions)

Institutions	Mean	Standard Deviation
College 1	82.90	18.23
College 2	71.30	14.20
College 3	73.87	16.25
College 4	76.80	18.13
Overall	77.21	17.66

The Mean Score and Standard Deviation of the respondents in college-1 is 82.90 & 18.23 is the highest in all four colleges where as overall mean and SD is 77.21 & 17.66 as shown in the above table. The overall mean value of SES is indicating that the average Socio-Economic Status of Pre service teachers falls under the category of High Socio-Economic Status as per the instructions of the manual of the tool. The result shows that most of the Pre-Service Teachers studying in Guru Govind Singh Indraprastha University had having High Socio-Economic Status. It is revealing that the majority of pre-service teachers in Delhi metro were of High economic status and able to get their teacher education training in public-private partnership owned university. They were able to afford comparatively high fee structure of privately run affiliated colleges of the university. It has been exclusively depicted through a multiple bar diagram.

Fig. 1 (Bar Diagram showing Mean and Standard Deviation of Pre-Service Teachers' SES)
To know more exclusively about SES of Pre-Service Teachers, another table no. 2 was created on the basis of sub-dimensions of Socio-Economic Status Scale.

Table No. 2 (Showing Sub-Dimension wise SES of Pre-Service Teachers)

Sr.No.	SES (Raw Score)	Frequencies (out of 333)	Interpretation of scores	Percentage
1.	92 and above	074	Very High Status	22.22%
2.	68 - 91	153	High Status	45.95%
3.	44 - 67	102	Average Status	30.63%
4.	32 - 43	004	Low Status	01.20%
5.	20 - 31	000	Very Low Status	0

The above table is showing that High Socio-Economic Status pre-service teachers had having highest percentage (45.95%) amongst all five sub-dimensions. That means High SES Pre-Service Teachers were in maximum number, studying in the University. The table is also revealing that Average SES and Very High SES Pre-Service Teachers were following the trend in the University. Whereas Low SES and Very Low SES pre-service teachers were in outnumber. Very Low SES Pre-Service Teachers' percentage is just zero therefore this kind of sub-dimension of SES has not been taken for further discussion. All these five sub-dimensions of SES has been exclusively depicted through a multiple Bar Diagram.

Fig. 2 (Bar Diagram showing frequencies & falling percentage of Pre-Service Teachers as per sub-dimensions of their Socio-Economic Status)

B. Motivation of Pre-Service Teachers:

To know motivation of Pre-Service Teachers Mean and SD were calculated.

Table No. 3 (Showing Mean & SD of Motivation of Pre-Service Teachers in different Institutions)

Institution	Mean	Standard Deviation
College -1	36.41	11.80
College-2	33.82	6.64
College-3	44.20	8.04
Colege-4	40.45	11.01
Overall	39.71	10.68

The Table no. 3 shows that the overall mean value of total motivation is 39.71 which depict near average motivation of the pre service teachers according to the manual of the tool. The mean and SD regarding motivation have been well depicted through the bar diagram (Fig.3)

Fig. 3 (Bar Diagram showing Mean and Standard Deviation of Total Motivation)

C. Achievement of Pre-Service Teachers:

Table No. 4 (Showing Mean and SD related to Achievement of Pre-Service Teachers)

Institutions	Mean	Standard Deviation
College -1	75.42	4.73
College-2	68.79	6.85
College-3	73.64	5.51
Colege-4	72.60	5.03
Overall	73.38	5.60

Table 4. reveals the mean achievement value of pre-service teachers. The overall mean value is 73.38, which falls in the category of Average achievement on a self constructed tool. The Mean Achievement value and its standard deviation have been depicted with the help of multiple bar diagram.

Fig. 4 (Bar Diagram showing Mean and SD of Pre-Service Teachers' Achievement)

D. (a) Relationship between Socio-Economic Status & Achievement:

Table No. 5 (Showing Correlation between SES & Achievement)

N	R	P	Significant
333	.303**	.000	YES

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table No. 5 reveals that there is significant correlation between SES and Achievement of pre-service teachers. It means SES of pre service teachers brings impact on achievement of Pre-Service Teachers. To check the correlation between SES and Achievement in some another statistical way, it was decided to make only two sub-dimensions of SES i.e. **Below Average SES & Above Average SES** and another table no. 6 was created to study t-Value between them.

Table No. 6 (Showing t-Value of Achievement across *Below Average & Above Average SES*)

Variable	Socio Economic Status (SES)	N	Mean	SD	t-Value
Achievement	Below Average SES	166	72.1205	5.58222	4.198**
	Above Average SES	167	74.6347	5.34627	

*Significant at 95%

** Significant at 99%

In the above table no.6 different SES sub-dimensions were divided into only two dimensions as *Below Average SES & Above Average SES*. Socio-Economic Status of pre-service teachers is significantly correlated at 99 % to their achievement. Those having above average SES does better than below average SES Pre Service Teachers because better socio-economic status provide better environment and resources to the individuals. Thus they grab the opportunities enthusiastically and bring better achievement.

D (b) Relationship between Motivation & Achievement:

Table No. 7 (Showing Correlation between Motivation and Achievement)

N	R	P	Significant
333	.206**	.000	YES

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table No.7 reveals that correlation between Motivation and Achievement is .206 which is significant but not strong enough. It means that Motivation plays some role in getting achievement of pre service teachers. A highly motivated pre-service teacher can do well regarding their achievement.

E. Joint Contributions of SES & Motivation on Achievement:

Step-wise Regression Analysis done towards the joint contribution of SES and Motivation on independent variable Achievement.

Table

No. 8 (Showing Model Summary)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.348 ^a	.121	.115	5.26714

a. Predictors: (Constant), MAT, SES

As shown in the above Table no. 8, model summary has been described. Here MAT and SES are Predictor variables towards Achievement of Pre service teachers. The above table reveals that R Square =.121 refers to Pearson's r correlation coefficient and this R Square value is farther away to 1. So there is weaker association between the predictor variables i.e. MAT & SES in the contribution of Achievement. The two predictors explain that there is 12.1 % joint contribution on the achievement of pre service teachers. R value .348 is showing the significance of Joint contribution of SES and Motivation on the Achievement of pre-service Teachers.

Table No. 9 (Showing ANOVA^b regarding Multiple Regression)

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	1257.452	2	628.726	22.663	.000 ^a
Residual	9155.112	330	27.743		
Total	10412.565	332			

a. Predictors: (Constant), MAT, SES

b.Dependent Variable: Achievement

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b. Dependent Variable: Achievement

Table No. 9 reveals that $P > .000$ therefore SES & MAT may significantly predict the achievement of the pre-service teachers

Table No. 10 (Showing Coefficients^a regarding Multiple Regression Analysis)

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	62.908	1.593		39.483	.000
SES	.089	.016	.282	5.417	.000
MAT	.090	.027	.172	3.304	.001

a. Dependent Variable: Achievement

Table No. 10 shows that SES has greater Beta .282 than MAT .172 so Socio Economic Status can be considered as more influencing or reliable predictor than MAT towards achievement.

F. JOINT CONTRIBUTION OF SES & MOTIVATION ON ATTITUDE:

To check the joint contribution of Motivation and SES on Teaching attitude of pre-service teachers multiple regressions was analyzed.

Table No.11 (Showing Model Summary)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.093 ^a	.009	.003	34.50739

a. Predictors: (Constant) MAT, SES

As shown in the Table no.11 model summary has been described. Here MAT and SES are Predictor variables towards Teaching Attitude of Pre service teachers. The above table reveals that R Square = .009 refers to Pearson's r correlation coefficient and this R Square value is very much farther away to 1. So there is very weaker association between the predictor variables i.e. MAT & SES on the Teaching Attitude of Pre service teachers. The two predictors explain that there is .9 % joint contribution on the Teaching Attitude of pre service teachers.

Table No. 12 (Showing ANOVA^b regarding Multiple Regression)

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	3432.507	2	1716.253	1.441	.238 ^a
Residual	392950.790	330	1190.760		
Total	396383.297	332			

a. Predictors: (Constant), MAT, SES

b. Dependent Variable: TAI [Attitude]

Table No. 12 reveals that $P < .238$ therefore SES & MAT may not significantly predict the Teaching Attitude of the pre service teachers.

Table No. 13 (Showing Coefficients^a regarding Multiple Regression Analysis)

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	241.017	10.438		23.090	.000
SES	.141	.108	.072	1.303	.194
MAT	-.221	.179	-.068	-1.240	.216

a. Dependent Variable: TAI

Table No. 13 shows that SES has greater Beta .72 than MAT .068 so Socio Economic Status can be considered as more influencing or reliable predictor than MAT towards Teaching Attitude of the pre service teachers.

DISCUSSION

The present study was a study of socio-economic status and motivation of pre-service teachers in relation to their achievement and attitude towards teaching in Guru Govind Singh Indraprastha University, New Delhi. The study was conducted to know about the correlation amongst socio- economic status, motivation and achievement of Pre-Service Teachers. Majority of Pre Service Teachers Studying in Guru Govind Singh Indraprastha University, Delhi, were of High Economic Status i.e.45.95 % Pre-Service Teachers were of High Economic Status. Around one fourth (22.22 %) of Pre-Service Teachers were of Very High Economic Status while Low Socio-Economic Status Pre-Service Teachers were only 1.20 % of the total samples taken for the study. None of the Pre-Service Teachers found in sub-dimension related to Very Low Economic Status. Socio-Economic Status is correlated to the Motivation of Pre-Service Teachers but not very strongly influence their total motivation. But, Very High Economic Status Pre-Service Teachers had highest level of total Motivation. Regarding total motivation of would be teachers, it was revealed that majority of Pre-Service Teachers had below Average or near Average Level of total or general Motivation. It was very interesting to see that Socio-Economic Status of Pre-Service Teachers is very significantly correlated to their Achievement. It was seen that Very High Economic Status Pre-Service Teachers had highest level of Achievement. Motivation of Pre-Service Teachers is strongly correlated to their academic achievement. Higher level of Motivation was correlated to the High Economic Status Pre-Service Teachers. Motivation Pre-Service Teachers is correlated to their Achievement. Majority of Pre-Service Teachers had Average Achievement (which is off course First Division & First Division with Distinction as per GGSIPU evaluation criterion.) Achievement and SES of Pre-Service Teachers are highly correlated to each other. Motivation and SES of Pre-Service Teachers together strongly predict their Achievement. In joint contribution of SES and Motivation towards Achievement, Socio-Economic Status is more significant / influencing than Motivation in the prediction of Achievement of Pre-Service Teachers.

CONCLUSIONS

The findings of the present study highlighted the existing psycho-social traits of Secondary level Pre-Service Teachers in Guru Govind Singh Indraprastha University, Delhi. It clearly revealed from the data analysis that majority of respondents, studying in the university, have High Socio-Economic Status. High Socio-Economic Status Pre-Service Teachers showed better level of Motivation as well as their Achievement during their course work. The study also revealed that Very High Socio-Economic Status Pre-Service Teachers had had highest level of Motivation and Achievement. Thus it can be concluded that motivation and socio-economic status both are correlated to the achievement of pre-service teachers. It was

also found that the Socio-Economic Status and Motivation are interrelated to each other. It means that the socio-economic status of a pre-service teacher influence his/her total motivation and also brings some impact on their achievement. In the joint contribution of SES and Motivation it was SES that influences the achievement of the pre-service teachers more significantly. The institutions should also indentify the Low Socio-Economic Status Pre-Service Teachers very honestly and provide all possible assistance & guidance to the needy so that they may concentrate solely on their study during the course of training. This way the effectiveness of teacher education would increase.

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